

Bridges and Barriers to Participation: Supporting Sociologists at Small and Community Colleges

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1. Are you currently a member of the Southern Sociological Society?

- Yes
- No

2. Are you currently employed or have you ever been employed at a small or community college?

We define small colleges are those with fewer than 3,000 undergraduate students and community colleges as those that primarily grant associate degrees.

- I am currently employed at a small or community college
- I used to be employed at a small or community college
- I have never been employed at a small or community college

First, we are interested in learning about your institution. If you have worked at multiple small or community colleges, please refer to your most recent employer.

3. What is the estimated undergraduate enrollment in your program or major? _____

4. If your program grants graduate degrees, what is the estimated graduate student enrollment? _____

5. How many full-time faculty does your department currently employ? _____

6. How many adjunct or part-time faculty does your department currently employ?

7. In dollars, about how much institutional support can you expect to receive each year for conference attendance? _____

8. In dollars, about how much institutional support can you expect to receive each year for professional development? _____

Next, we would like to know a little about you.

9. What is your current professional title?

- Graduate Student

- Adjunct Instructor
- Instructor
- Assistant Professor
- Associate Professor
- Professor
- Other (please specify) _____

10. Which of the following best describes your position?

- Non-tenure track
- Tenure track
- Tenured
- Other (please specify) _____

11. How long were you employed at a small and/or community college? *Cumulative, if employed at multiple institutions.*

- Less than one year
- 1 - 3 years
- 4 - 6 years
- 7 - 9 years
- 10 years or more

12. Have you ever departed or made a decision to vacate your position as a faculty member at a small or community college?

- No
- Yes

13. Which of the following best fits your reason(s) for leaving? *Select all that apply.*

- Partner employment
- Decision to change career paths
- Challenges related to diversity, equity, and inclusion
- Issues with departmental work environments
- Social environment for single faculty members
- Proximity to family
- Superior offer from similar institution
- Lack of institutional support for research and/or professional development
- Other (please specify) _____

14. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / third gender
- Transgender
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

15. What is your age?

- Less than 21 years
- 22 - 32 years
- 33 - 43 years
- 44 - 54 years
- 55 - 65 years
- Over 65
- Prefer not to answer

16. What is your race?

- White
- Black or African American
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian or Pacific Islander
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

Lastly, we are interested in learning about your experiences with SSS.

17. Please indicate how much you consider each statement weighs on your decision to participate in the SSS annual conference.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Present and receive feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Learn new ideas for engaging in research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Share and learn about teaching strategies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Share and learn about department leadership practices	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Share best practices via roundtable discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide or receive mentoring	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Network and build community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Connect with people who represent diverse communities	<input type="radio"/>				
Build coalitions and consortiums	<input type="radio"/>				
Present your institution to a regional audience	<input type="radio"/>				
Serve in a role for a professional organization	<input type="radio"/>				
Build a strong portfolio for promotion and tenure	<input type="radio"/>				
Serve on a committee in a professional organization	<input type="radio"/>				
Stay within the south for a professional organization	<input type="radio"/>				
Attendance is typical for my department	<input type="radio"/>				
Location of the conference	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Please indicate how much do you consider each statement to weigh on your decision NOT to participate in the SSS annual conference?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Conference carbon footprint	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cost of registration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cost of travel and lodging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of accessible spaces and technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of an established network of scholars attending	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of childcare	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of encouragement from institution to attend	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of familiarity with conference logistics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of institutional funding	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Lack of mentoring opportunities	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of time available to leave home duties	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of time available to take academic leave	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of visibility of historically marginalized groups	<input type="radio"/>				
Location in the southern region of the United States	<input type="radio"/>				
Negative micro-politics	<input type="radio"/>				
Unsure that my health, wellbeing, and safety are assured	<input type="radio"/>				

19. Is there anything else that you would like to share about your decision to participate or not in SSS?

20. What is your level of familiarity with the SSS [Distinguished Lecture Award](#)?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Very familiar

21. What is your level of familiarity with the application process to be selected as a site to host the lecturer?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Very familiar

22. Has your program ever applied as a host site for this award?

- Never applied
- Applied but not selected
- Applied and selected
- Don't know

23. What characteristics would you consider a barrier to your interest in applying to be a lectureship site? *Select all that apply.*

- Lack of information
- Cost sharing
- Lack of institutional resources or support
- Size or design of your program or major
- Lack of time for organizing the event
- Lack of time for putting on the event
- In-person event
- Virtual event
- Topics that do not fit

24. Based on your answers to the previous question, what could SSS do to make this award work better for your institution or increase the likelihood that you would apply to be a lectureship site?

25. What do you consider the greatest needs for yourself and colleagues at your small or community college?

26. Is there anything else that you would like to share with us regarding SSS?